

DIVERSIFYING BEYOND THE FIELDS: A REVIEW OF EMPLOYMENT PATTERNS IN THE RURAL NON-FARM SECTOR

Naveen Sharma

Research Scholar, Sri Guru Granth Sahib World University

ABSTRACT

The rural non-farm sector (RNFS) has grown significantly over the past few decades, evolving into a vital component of rural livelihoods across developing countries, especially in India. This paper presents a systematic review of key studies exploring employment diversification in the RNFS, highlighting patterns, determinants, and implications for rural development. The literature reveals a complex interplay of pull and push factors—including declining farm profitability, urban proximity, education, caste, gender, and infrastructure—that shape participation in non-farm employment. While some studies emphasize the role of RNFS in reducing rural poverty and unemployment, others point to structural inequalities and regional disparities in access and outcomes. Despite the growing policy focus on rural transformation, major empirical gaps remain concerning occupational preferences, earnings, and time use within the RNFS. This review concludes by identifying critical directions for future research and policy, particularly the need for region-specific evidence and inclusive employment strategies.

Keywords: Rural Non-Farm Sector (RNFS), Employment Diversification, Rural Livelihoods, Non-Farm Employment, Rural Development

1. INTRODUCTION

The transformation of rural economies in developing countries has increasingly centered around the diversification of employment into non-farm sectors. With declining agricultural returns, fluctuating productivity, and increasing land fragmentation, rural households are shifting to alternative income sources in services, construction, trade, and manufacturing.

India exemplifies this transition, where the rural non-farm sector contributes significantly to employment generation and income stability. However, the nature of this diversification is far from uniform. The process varies by region, gender, caste, education, and access to infrastructure. This paper reviews key empirical studies from India and abroad to understand the evolving landscape of non-farm employment, the determinants of participation, and its socio-economic implications.

The review also uncovers research gaps, particularly in state-level and micro-level analyses, and proposes directions for future studies to inform more inclusive and regionally targeted rural development policies.

2. DATA AND METHODOLOGY

This is a review-based study, and the methodology involves a thematic synthesis of 50+ empirical studies from India and other developing countries (e.g., Vietnam, Ghana, Ethiopia, Bhutan, and Indonesia). Sources include peer-reviewed journal articles, NSSO/PLFS-based studies, econometric model-based research, and policy evaluation reports published between 1990 and 2022.

The analysis is organized around the following themes:

- Structural trends in RNFS

- Socio-economic determinants of participation
- Gender dimensions
- Sectoral composition
- Income and inequality implications
- Regional and policy perspectives

The research also identifies gaps in existing literature using comparative reading and highlights under-researched domains, especially pertaining to occupational distribution and micro-level time-use evidence in RNFS.

3. THEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW

3.1 Structural Shifts and Drivers of RNFS Employment

Studies by Hazell & Haggblade (1990), Reardon et al. (2006), and Binswanger-Mkhize (2012) confirm that RNFS has become central to rural economic transformation. These shifts are driven both by the distress in agriculture (e.g., low returns, high input costs) and opportunities created by urbanization, infrastructure expansion, and globalization.

Ghuman (2008) and Singhal & Bains (2018) emphasize that the stagnation in agricultural employment has pushed rural workers toward non-farm sectors, often without adequate policy or institutional support.

3.2 Determinants of Participation in Non-Farm Employment

Key individual and household-level determinants include:

Education (Kongolo & Bamgose, 2002; Ranjan, 2009)

Caste and Social Group (S. Kaur et al., 2010; Suresh, 2017)

Landholding and Wealth (Reardon et al., 2006; Tamayo & Vasco, 2017)

Gender and Age (Srivastava & Srivastava, 2010; Bezu & Barrett, 2012)

Macro-determinants such as infrastructure, electrification, and urban proximity (A. Kaur et al., 2019) have been shown to create enabling conditions for non-farm employment growth.

3.3 Gender Dimensions and Social Exclusion

Despite increased participation, women in RNFS are mostly concentrated in informal and low-paying jobs (Cliche, 2011; Goswami & Bhattacharya, 2014). Gender wage gaps (Yoo, 2003) and caste-based exclusion further restrict women's economic empowerment.

Mulia et al. (2021) and Asih (2021) caution that while RNFS offers income opportunities, it may also exacerbate social tensions due to widening gaps between marginalized and mainstream groups.

3.4 Sectoral Composition and Informality

The sector is dominated by informal employment in construction, services, and micro-enterprises (Jatav, 2012; A. Kaur et al., 2019). Wage employment is limited and formal jobs are scarce. Home-based and seasonal work remains common, especially among women and the poor.

The studies suggest that while RNFS can absorb surplus rural labor, it rarely guarantees stable or high-income employment unless supplemented by skill development and financial access (Ramesh & Patrick, 2019).

3.5 RNFS, Income Inequality, and Poverty

There is mixed evidence on whether RNFS reduces inequality:

Luo & Zhu (2006) and Kalalto (2016) found that RNFS reduces income gaps by raising earnings of poor households.

However, Senadza (2010) and Bezu & Barrett (2012) argue that RNFS may increase inequality if better-off households capture more lucrative opportunities.

Studies using advanced econometric techniques (e.g., Pattayat et al., 2022) show that RNFS employment has the potential to reduce poverty if it aligns with infrastructure and service sector growth. The summary of review literature has been presented in the following table.

Table 1: Summary of Review of Literature

Sr. No.	Name of Authors	Focus Area/Objective	Data and Methodology	Key Findings
1	(Hazell & Haggblade, 1990)	Explore rural-urban growth linkages in India	Secondary data; model-based economic analysis	Strong linkages exist; RNF growth driven by agriculture, infrastructure, and urban demand
2	(Visaria, 1995)	Discuss trends and issues in RNF employment in India	Review of NSSO and other secondary data	RNF employment rising but quality and income gaps persist
3	(Fan et al., 2000)	Examine impact of public spending on rural growth and poverty	Time-series econometric models; Indian district-level data	Spending on rural infrastructure, education, and R&D significantly reduces poverty
4	(Mehta, 2002)	Analyse role of non-farm economy in rural development	Secondary data and conceptual analysis	RNF sector vital for rural development and employment generation
5	(Kongolo & Bamgose, 2002)	Assess rural women's participation in development in South Africa	Case study of 3 villages; qualitative analysis	Education and skills key for women's participation in RNF; social norms limit access
6	(Kundu, 2003)	Studied rural-urban links in the post-reform era	Secondary data; urban-rural interface perspective	Despite rural-urban linkages, this process of urbanisation has not led to increased possibilities for rural nonfarm employees. Reforms needed to support

				inclusive rural employment
7	(S. Singh, 2003)	Economic analysis of farm vs. non-farm employment in Punjab	Primary survey; comparative income and employment analysis	Non-farm employment crucial for rural diversification; returns depend on education and location
8	(Ghuman, 2008)	Examine socio-economic crisis in rural Punjab	Conceptual and qualitative analysis	Agrarian crisis pushing labour towards low-productivity RNF jobs
9	(Vatta et al., 2008)	Analyse household-level rural employment and income variation in Punjab	Primary data from selected villages	High variation in RNF income; access to capital and landholding size are key determinants
10	(Ranjan, 2009)	Assess growth of rural non-farm employment in Uttar Pradesh	NSSO data; trend analysis	RNF employment is increasing but regional disparities remain high
11	(S. Kaur et al., 2010)	Explore prospects of RNF employment and welfare	ASARC Working Paper using secondary datasets	RNF employment can improve welfare but is not uniformly accessible
12	(Srivastava & Srivastava, 2010)	Study gender dimensions of employment and outcomes in rural India	NSSO unit-level data; gender-disaggregated analysis	Women concentrated in low-paid RNF work; access to decent jobs limited by education and mobility
13	(Senadza, 2010)	Examine determinants and welfare effects of RNF income diversification in Ghana	Ghana Living Standards Survey; econometric modelling	Education, infrastructure access, and gender influence diversification; positive welfare effects
14	(Abraham, 2011)	Impact of agrarian distress on rural non-farm employment in India	NSSO data; empirical analysis	Agrarian distress pushes workforce into low-end RNF activities without significant income gain
15	(Cliche, 2011)	Empowerment of rural women through non-farm employment and ICT in Latin America	Case studies and conceptual analysis	ICT initiatives can promote RNF participation among women if gender barriers are addressed

16	(Bezu & Barrett, 2012)	Examine whether rural poor in Ethiopia benefit over time from RNF employment	Panel data; econometric modelling	Time is not always on the side of the poor; initial wealth matters for sustained RNF participation
17	(Binswanger-Mkhize, 2012)	Structural change and RNF sector growth in India from 1960–2010	Macro-level secondary data; structural transformation lens	RNF sector growth insufficient to absorb excess agricultural labour
18	(Jatav, 2012).	Extent of casualization in RNF employment in India	NSSO rounds; trend and regression analysis	Casualization has increased, especially among women and disadvantaged castes
19	(Reddy et al., 2014)	Link RNF employment to rural transformation in India	Village Dynamics Studies in South Asia (ICRISAT); multi-village surveys	RNF employment rising but mostly distress-driven and unproductive
20	(Goswami & Bhattacharya, 2014)	RNF employment trends and issues in Assam	NSSO and field data; descriptive analysis	RNF sector underdeveloped; policy neglect and poor infrastructure major constraints
21	(Rahut et al., 2015)	Assess RNF employment's role in income and inequality in Bhutan	Bhutan Living Standards Survey; econometric analysis	RNF jobs contribute significantly to income and inequality reduction
22	(Hoai et al., 2016)	Examine growth and structural transformation in Vietnam	Macroeconomic data from 2000s; structural change framework	Vietnam has experienced a successful transformation with RNF playing a key transitional role
23	(Kalalto, 2016)	Determinants of participation in RNF employment in Ethiopia	Household survey; probit regression	Education, infrastructure, and asset ownership significantly influence RNF participation
24	(Suresh, 2017)	Examine nature and characteristics of RNF sector in India	Secondary data review; thematic categorization	RNF sector is heterogeneous and growing, but still informal and under regulated

25	(Tamayo & Vasco, 2017)	Determinants of RNF employment and earnings in Ecuador	Household survey; OLS regression	Education, location, and access to credit positively impact RNF income and participation
26	(A. Kaur et al., 2019)	Explore nature, pattern, and determinants of employment diversification in rural India	Unit-level NSSO data; econometric analysis	Education, caste, and landholding size are key factors for diversification into RNF sector
27	(Singhal & Bains, 2018)	Assess growth of RNF sector and impact on migration in India	Secondary data from Census, NSSO, and NFHS; descriptive analysis	RNF sector contributes to reducing distress migration but lacks formal structure
28	(Ramesh & Patrick, 2019)	Study NABARD's rural entrepreneurship development program and its effectiveness	Case study approach; program reports	NABARD's programs significantly promote RNF employment through entrepreneurship training
29	(G. Singh, 2020)	Analyse access to RNF employment in Bihar and Punjab	NSSO and primary survey data; mixed methods	Caste, education, and infrastructure impact access to RNF jobs
30	(S. Singh & Bhogal, 2020)	Examine long-term changes in agricultural labourers' employment in Punjab	Longitudinal study over three decades	Agricultural labourers are diversifying into RNF jobs due to declining viability of farm work
31	(Asih, 2021)	Investigate off-farm labour participation in Indonesia	Rural household survey; regression analysis	Education level and landholding significantly affect participation in off-farm work
32	(Kapoor et al., 2021)	Analyse drivers and impact of RNF employment in Uttar Pradesh	NSSO unit-level data; multinomial logit model	Access to roads, education, and assets positively influence RNF employment
33	(Mulia et al., 2021)	Examine economic and non-economic impacts of RNF activities in	Literature review; policy analysis	RNF contributes to resilience and sustainability of rural livelihoods

		Vietnam		
34	(Pattayat et al., 2022)	Investigate RNF job creation and rural poverty reduction in India	NSSO data; panel regression models	RNF employment significantly reduces rural poverty and inequality
35	(Abraham, 2023)	Explore whether RNF employment is shifting or diversifying	PLFS and earlier NSS rounds; trend and decomposition analysis	RNF growth is slow and mostly diversification, not structural shift
36	(Das & Deka, 2023)	Examine determinants and wellbeing implications of RNF employment in NE India	NSSO data; ordered probit and logit models	RNF jobs improve household wellbeing; determinants include education, access to infrastructure
37	(Pattayat et al., 2023)	Examine gender wage gaps in RNF sector in India	PLFS data; Blinder-Oaxaca decomposition	Substantial gender wage gaps exist; education and sectoral segregation are key contributors
38	(Pattayat & Parida, 2024)	Long-term analysis of RNF determinants	NSSO data	Education, skills, infrastructure, and industrial growth strongly influence RNF. Shift from agriculture is driven by push and pull factors at different periods.

4. RESEARCH GAPS IDENTIFIED

Despite abundant studies, key gaps remain:

1. **Limited state-level evidence** on RNFS diversification, especially in less-studied regions.
2. **Lack of micro-level data** on occupational preferences, working hours, and earnings across professions.
3. **Insufficient focus on informal sector dynamics**, including mobility, work insecurity, and barriers to entry.
4. **Under-representation of female perspectives** in non-farm employment and access to vocational opportunities.

5. CONCLUSION

The rural non-farm sector has become a cornerstone of rural employment diversification, particularly in the face of agrarian distress and limited job creation in agriculture. While several studies highlight its potential to generate income and reduce rural poverty, systemic barriers—social, structural, and geographic—continue to affect participation and outcomes.

The review underscores the need for region-specific studies and gender-sensitive policy interventions. Investments in education, infrastructure, and access to finance must accompany RNFS promotion to ensure it offers not just employment, but sustainable and equitable livelihoods.

REFERENCES

1. Abraham, V. (2011). *Agrarian distress and rural non-farm sector employment in India* (No. 3575; MPRAPA). <https://ideas.repec.org/p/pramprapa/35275.html>
2. Abraham, V. (2023). The Slow Emergence of Rural Non-farm Sector Employment in India: Shift or Diversification? *The Indian Journal of Labour Economics*, 66(3), 661–685. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41027-023-00452-7>
3. Asih, D. N. (2021). Transformation of labor participation on off-farm diversification: insights from rural households in Indonesia. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 892(1), 12–15. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/892/1/012015>
4. Bezu, S., & Barrett, C. (2012). Employment Dynamics in the Rural Nonfarm Sector in Ethiopia: Do the Poor Have Time on Their Side? *Journal of Development Studies*, 48(9), 1223–1240. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220388.2012.671476>
5. Binswanger-Mkhize, H. P. (2012). *India 1960-2010: Structural Change, the Rural Nonfarm Sector, and the Prospects for Agriculture*. <https://doi.org/10.1.1.406.2420>
6. Cliche, G. (2011). *Rural Women's Empowerment in Nonfarm Employment Issues for ICT Initiatives and Territorial Policies in Latin America*. <https://www.un.org/womenwatch/daw/csw/csw56/egm/Cliche-EP-7-EGM-RW-30-Sep-2011.pdf>
7. Das, G. K., & Deka, N. (2023). Rural Non-farm Sector Employment in the North-Eastern Region of India: Determinants and Implications for Well-being. *Margin: The Journal of Applied Economic Research*, 17(3–4), 279–314. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00252921241229799>
8. Fan, S., Hazell, P., & Thorat, S. (2000). Government Spending, Growth and Poverty in Rural India. *American Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 82(4), 1038–1051. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/1244540>
9. Ghuman, R. S. (2008). Socio-Economic Crisis in Rural Punjab. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 43(7), 12–15. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/40277604>
10. Goswami, C., & Bhattacharya, M. (2014). Rural Non Farm Employment in Assam: Trends and Issues. *Space and Culture, India*, 2(1), 14. <https://doi.org/10.20896/saci.v2i1.38>
11. Hazell, P., & Haggblade, S. (1990). Rural–Urban Growth Linkages in India. *Indian Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 46.
12. Hoai, D., Tarp, F., Seventer, D., & Ho, H. (2016). *Growth and structural transformation in Vietnam during the 2000s*. <https://doi.org/10.35188/UNU-WIDER/2016/152-9>
13. Jatav, M. (2012). Extent of casualisation in rural non-farm workforce of India: what does recent national sample survey data reveal? *Journal of Social and Economic*

- Development, 14, 65+.*
<https://link.gale.com/apps/doc/A307789019/AONE?u=anon~a0c7945a&sid=googleScholar&xid=beb389f1>
14. Kalalto, G. (2016). Determinants of employment participation in rural non-farm activities. *Journal of Poverty, Investment and Development, 29*, 10–21.
<https://www.iiste.org/Journals/index.php/JPID/issue/view/2726>
 15. Kapoor, S., Kumar, A., & Saroj, S. (2021). Rural non-farm employment in Uttar Pradesh, India: drivers and impact. *Agricultural Economics Research Review, 34*(1), 33–50. <https://doi.org/10.5958/0974-0279.2021.00003.3>
 16. Kaur, A., Arora, A., & Singh, S. P. (2019). Employment Diversification in Rural India: Nature, Pattern and Determinants. *AGER, 27*, 189–226.
<https://doi.org/10.4422/ager.2019.02>
 17. Kaur, S., Kulkarni, V., Gaiha, R., & Pandey, M. (2010). Prospects of Non-Farm Employment and Welfare in Rural Areas. *Australian National University, Australia South Asia Research Centre, ASARC Working Papers.*
 18. Kongolo, M., & Bamgose, O. O. (2002). Participation of rural women in development: A case study of Tsheseng, Thintwa and Makhalaneng villages, South Africa. *Journal of International Women's Studies, 4*(1), 79–92.
<https://vc.bridgew.edu/jiws/vol4/iss1/6>
 19. Kundu, A. (2003). Urbanisation and Urban Governance: Search for a Perspective beyond Neo-Liberalism. *Economic and Political Weekly, 38*(29), 3079–3087.
<http://www.jstor.org/stable/4413810>
 20. Luo, X., & Zhu, N. (2006). *Nonfarm Activity And Rural Income Inequality : A Case Study Of Two Provinces In China.* The World Bank. <https://doi.org/10.1596/1813-9450-3811>
 21. Mehta, G. S. (2002). *Non-farm economy and rural development.*
https://niti.gov.in/planningcommission.gov.in/docs/reports/sereport/ser/stdy_nfeco.pdf
 22. Mulia, R., Simelton, E., Nguyen, T., & Jirström, M. (2021). Non-Farm Activities and Impacts beyond the Economy of Rural Households in Vietnam: A Review and Link to Policies. *Sustainability, 13*, 10182. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su131810182>
 23. Pattayat, S. S., & Parida, J. K. (2024). Drivers of Rural Non-farm Sector Employment in India, 1983–2019. *South Asia Economic Journal, 25*(1), 45–73.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/13915614231221649>
 24. Pattayat, S. S., Parida, J. K., & Awasthi, I. C. (2022). Reducing Rural Poverty Through Non-farm Job Creation in India. *The Indian Journal of Labour Economics, 65*(1), 137–160. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41027-022-00359-9>
 25. Pattayat, S. S., Parida, J. K., & Paltasingh, K. R. (2023). Gender Wage Gap among Rural Non-farm Sector Employees in India: Evidence from Nationally Representative Survey. *Review of Development and Change, 28*(1), 22–44.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/09722661231172867>

26. Rahut, D. B., Jena, P. R., Ali, A., Behera, B., & Chhetri, N. B. (2015). Rural Nonfarm Employment, Income, and Inequality: Evidence from Bhutan. *Asian Development Review*, 32(2), 65–94. https://doi.org/10.1162/ADEV_a_00052
27. Ramesh, M., & Patrick, A. (2019). Rural Non-farm schemes of NABARD-A study of rural entrepreneurship development programme. *Pramana Research Journal*, 9(1), 485–492. https://www.pramanaresearch.org/gallery/prj-s295_1.pdf
28. Ranjan, S. (2009). Growth of rural non-farm employment in Uttar Pradesh: Reflections from recent data. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 44(4). <https://www.epw.in/journal/2009/04/special-articles/growth-rural-non-farm-employment-uttar-pradesh-reflections-recent>
29. Reardon, T., Berdegue, J. A., Barrett, C. B., & Stamoulis, K. (2006). *Household Income Diversification into Rural Nonfarm Activities: Transforming The Rural Non-farm Economy opportunities and threats in the developing world*. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=1846821
30. Reddy, D. N., Reddy, A., Nagaraj, N., & Bantilan, C. (2014). *Rural Non-Farm Employment and Rural Transformation in India* (No. 57; Working Paper Series). <http://vdsa.icrisat.ac.in/Include/reports/wps57.pdf>
31. Senadza, B. (2010). *Non-Farm Income Diversification In Rural Ghana; Determinants And Implications For Income Distribution And Welfare* [University of Ghana]. <http://ugspace.ug.edu.gh/handle/123456789/7015?show=full>
32. Singh, G. (2020). Access to Non-farm Employment in Contemporary India: A Study of Bihar and Punjab. *Social Change*, 50(4), 532–547. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0049085720957512>
33. Singh, S. (2003). *An economic analysis of farm and non-farm employment in rural Punjab* [Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana]. <https://krishikosh.egranth.ac.in/handle/1/5810015797>
34. Singh, S., & Bhogal, S. (2020). Punjab's Agricultural Labourers in Transition: A Longitudinal Study of Three Decades. *Review of Rural Affairs*, 55(26). <https://www.epw.in/journal/2020/26-27/review-rural-affairs/punjab-agricultural-labourers-transition.html>
35. Singhal, K., & Bains, G. (2018). Critical analysis of the growth of rural non-farm sector in India and its impact on migration. *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, 5(3), 316–322. <https://www.jetir.org/papers/JETIR1803063.pdf>
36. Srivastava, N., & Srivastava, R. (2010). Women, Work, and Employment Outcomes in Rural India. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 45(28), 49–63. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/40736730>
37. Suresh. (2017). The study of nature and characteristics of rural non-farm sector in India. *International Journal of Management and Development Studies*, 6(4), 07–19. <https://www.ijmds.in/index.php/ijmds/article/view/271/252>
38. Tamayo, G., & Vasco, C. (2017). Determinants of non-farm employment and non-farm earnings in Ecuador: Cristian Vasco and Grace Natalie Tamayo. *CEPAL Review*, 2017, 53–67. <https://doi.org/10.18356/80b76a5e-en>

39. Vatta, K., Garg, B. R., & Sidhu, M. S. (2008). Rural Employment and Income: The Inter-household Variations in Punjab. *Agricultural Economics Research Review*, 21.
40. Visaria, P. (1995). Rural Non-Farm Employment in India: Trends and Issues for Research. *Indian Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 50(3), 275035.
<https://econpapers.repec.org/RePEc:ags:inijae:275035>
41. Yoo, G. (2003). Women in the Workplace: Gender and Wage Differentials. *Social Indicators Research*, 62/63, 365–385. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/27527100>